

HISTORY DEVELOPMENT OF SCREENING CENTERS IN UZBEKISTAN

M.M. Makhmudova

Urgench branch of Tashkent medical academy
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7780839>

Subject: Expansion of specialized medical care in Uzbekistan. The Expansion specialized medical help in Uzbekistan.

Relevance of a subject: In the course reforming of a health care system of Uzbekistan special attention was paid to improvement of medical care to mothers and children. The screening and perinatal centers, versatile children's hospitals were created. New, advanced methods of prevention and treatment of specific diseases took root. As a result decrease in level of diseases and mortality of mothers and children achieved. Experience of Uzbekistan in this case was generally recognized.

Research objective: To study and generalize experience of development of the screening help to mothers and children, on early detection of hereditary and dangerous diseases, prevention of early disability and mortality.

Research methods: chronological, statistical, comparative analysis and synthesis, comparison, etc.

Keywords: reproductive health, screening and perinatal centers, ultrasonography, tomograph, etc.

Тема: Расширение специализированной медицинской помощи в Узбекистане. The Expansion specialized medical help in Uzbekistan.

Актуальность темы: В ходе реформирование системы здравоохранения Узбекистана особое внимание было уделено совершенствованию медицинской помощи матерям и детям. Создавались скрининговые и перинатальные центры, многопрофильные детские больницы. Внедрялись новые, передовые методы профилактики и лечения специфических заболеваний. В результате добились снижение уровня заболеваний и смертности матерей и детей. Опыт Узбекистана в этом деле получило всеобщее признание.

Цель исследования: Изучить и обобщить опыт развития скрининговой помощи матерям и детям, по раннему выявлению наследственных и опасных болезней, предупреждение ранней инвалидности и смертности.

Методы исследования: хронологические, статистические, сравнительный анализ и синтез, сопоставление и т. д.

Ключевые слова: репродуктивное здоровье, скрининговые и перинатальные центры, УЗИ, томограф и т. д.

Since 1998 in Uzbekistan large-scale reform of a health care system in which special attention was paid to protection by motherhood and the childhood began. Demanded it a demographic situation of the country. By January 1, 2009, the number of inhabitants of the republic increased to 27 million people. From them, children up to 15 years made 38,5%, women of fertile age — 28,4% [1]. The problem of rendering necessary medical care to women and

children was coming, to learn about health of the child to his birth and to be prepared for the forthcoming childbirth. Early detection of a hereditary disease allowed to provide a timely initiation of treatment for prevention at the child of disability since the childhood. For this purpose creation complete sets screening centers of "Mother and the child" was required.

Very first in Uzbekistan — Priaralsky screening center of mother and child was created in 1997 in Nukus and served the population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm region. The efficiency of activity of this establishment in prevention of the birth of children with heavy deviations in development formed a basis for acceptance at the initiative of the President I.A. Karimov in 1998 of the State program "Screening of mother and child" and creation of similar institutions in all regions of Uzbekistan. During its performance the Republican center of screening of mother and child in Tashkent and its branches in 10 areas was created.

With opening screening center in Urgench the Priaralsky center was renamed — in Karakalpak. "In the course of creation screening centers in other regions to us many experts came to get acquainted with experience of the organization of activity of our establishment, — the director of the Karakalpak center of Amin Kalandarov told. — Today in the center there is a measured work. Daily we accept women with the weakened health. Work is a hard, and biggest award for it — the words of gratitude of families which we helped to find joy to raise healthy children" [2].

In further development and strengthening of screening service the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About additional measures for health protection of mother and the child, formation of healthy generation" of April 13, 2009 was important. Much attention to this service was paid also in "The state program about measures of strengthening and increase in a measure for strengthening of reproductive health, birth rate of the healthy child, education physically and spiritual generation", approved on July 1, 2009.

By 2008 in comparison with 1998, thanks to activity screening centers the birth rate of children with the diseases leading to disability in the republic decreased by 14% [2]. It became a telling argument at making decision on construction in the Jizzakh and Syr Darya regions screening centers. In the beginning, pregnant women of the Jizzakh and Syr Darya regions served the Samarkand regional and Republican screening center in Tashkent. In the spring of 2010 in Jizzakh and in Gulistan regional screening centers began to accept turning women. Thereby work on creation of regional branches of the Republican center where experts were engaged in early detection and prevention of congenital diseases was complete.

In 2010 in Tashkent the scientific conference devoted to a role of screening service in health protection of mother and child, providing the birth and education of healthy generation took place. In an action, along with doctors of Uzbekistan experts from Russia and Finland took part. As it was noted at a conference that in the republic it was annually carried out screening inspection more than 100 thousand pregnant women and about 500 thousand newborns [3]. It was an important factor of prevention of hereditary and congenital diseases, disability, health protection of mother and the child, the birth and education of healthy children.

In 2011, in Uzbekistan 5,9 million women and girls had annual medical examination, about 150 thousand pregnant women — screening inspection. More than 243 thousand pregnant women living in rural areas were provided free polyvitamins. Vaccination against infectious diseases at children made about 100 percent [4].

Implementation of state programs yielded noticeable positive results on improvement of mothers and children. The coverage of women contraceptive funds from 13,0% of 1991 up to 52,1% of 2011 increased. The indicator of infantile mortality, on 1000 newborns — with 35,5 in 1991 to 10,2 in 2012 decreased. The indicator of maternal mortality decreased with 65,3 in 1991 to 21,2 in 2012 [5]

Educational and medical institutions began to meet the international standards. In 2011, for the purpose of education and health care of reconstruction, capital repairs and equipment, the special Fund was created. WHO highly appreciated also national the "Health Protection of Mother and Child" model. On children's health care Uzbekistan entered among ten best countries of the world.

On November 25-26, 2011 in Tashkent the International symposium "National model of health protection of mother and child in Uzbekistan took place: "Healthy mother — the healthy child". In it is mute the CEO of WHO Margaret Chong, about 300 representatives of science and the international organizations in health sector recognized in the world took part. Addressing participants of a forum the President I.A. Karimov noted: "The generally recognized slogan — the principle "Healthy mother — the healthy child" on the essence was the uniting and mobilizing address to the population, became that priority which was lifted to the state and public level. ... Today we have all bases to say that for years of independent development almost capital base on which the country health care system" continues to be under construction and updated [6] is created.

Among achievements of Uzbekistan it was noted that the organization within the special state program of network modern screening centers of mother and child, allowed to reduce from 2000 more than by 1,7 times the birth of children with hereditary and degenerate diseases. In the republic it was carried out free vaccination of all children under two years that allowed us to liquidate completely such diseases as diphtheria, tetanus, poliomyelitis. Nearly 100 percent of children aged up to 14 years are twice a year covered by profound medical examinations, and women of fertile age — annually.

As a result of realization of a package of measures for the last 20 years maternal and infantile mortality in the country decreased more than by 3 times. Uzbekistan in the world ranking of 161 states made in 2011 by the International organization "Let's Save Children" took the 9th place among the countries of the world where best of all care for health of younger generation.

The participant of a forum, the head of office of children's surgery of the Madrid hospital Lorenzo Bonnie (Spain) noted: "In prevention of different pathologies among children as an important factor serves screening inspection of mother and child. Development in Uzbekistan services of screening, establishing timely rendering the medical and social care to pregnant women yield the good results in the birth of healthy generation, prevention of cardiological diseases among children" [7].

A lot of work on early detection of pathologies at pregnant women was carried out by staff of the Republican center "Screening of Mother and Child". Specialists of the center mastered new methods of diagnostics and prevention of various diseases which in the country were not diagnosed before and were not treated on early terms. The center was equipped with the biochemical analyzer which allowed to carry out the confirming diagnostics of a number of hereditary diseases of neuromuscular system and the pathological states which are followed by skeletal deformations.

As a result of complex actions for in 1991-2014 mortality of mothers in the country was reduced by 3,1 times, children — by 3,2 times. As a result of implementation of the Screening of Mother and Child program since 2000 by 1,8 times cases of the birth of children with congenital pathologies were reduced. It should be noted especially that for the last 5 years the birth rate of children with abnormal development was reduced by 1,3 times. The incidence of acute respiratory viral infections among children of 6-15 years decreased by 9,7%, pneumonia — for 49,1%, bronchitis — for 32,8%, scoliosis — for 32,7% [8].

By 2014 92 percent of children of the country on development indicators completely met standards of World Health Organization. For this reason the national model of health protection of mother and child realized in Uzbekistan "Healthy mother — the healthy child" is recognized as one of the effective strategy of achievement of the goals of development of the millennium.

In 2015 to structure of screening of Uzbekistan were 12 regional and the Republican Screening of Mother and Child center in Tashkent. They covered nearly 100 pregnant women screening researches in the countries [9]. Implementation of measures for prevention and early detection of congenital and hereditary pathology at pregnant women and newborns, allowed to reduce number of the birth of children with hereditary diseases and congenital malformations, to lift to the international level potential screening centers on prevention and treatment of a wide range of hereditary diseases. Further strengthening in this area of work will become an important step in the solution of problems of development of healthy generation of the country.

The resume

In article the history of creation and results of activity of the screenings-centres of Uzbekistan is told, their role in early revealing of illnesses of pregnant women and newborns is shown.

Резюме

В статье рассказывается история создания и результаты деятельности скрининг-центров Узбекистана, показывается их роль в раннем выявлении болезней беременных и новорождённых.

Literature:

1. "A national word", 2010, on January 30.
2. Healthy generation — a main goal of activity of new medical institutions // www.ut.uz. April, 2010.
3. To health of mother and child — constant attention//www.uza.uz. April, 2010.
4. The report of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov a cabinet meeting "About results of 2011 and priority problems of social and economic development of Uzbekistan in 2012" // "the East Truth", 2012, on February 19.
5. Development of primary health care in Uzbekistan: achievements and problems. — Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2013, page 11.
6. A speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov at opening of the international symposium "National model of health protection of mother and child in Uzbekistan: "Healthy mother — the healthy child" // www.Press-service.uz. November 26, 2011.

7. Progress of Uzbekistan in the sphere of medicine is worthy high admiration//www.uza.uz. November 24, 2011.
8. Reforms of a health care system: results and tasks on prospect // www.Press-service.uz. August 18, 2014.
9. Sharipova M. With care of the birth of the healthy child//www.minzdrav.uz.
7. Goncharova O.V. "Yosh sportchilarning jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish" o'quv qo'llanma T.: O'zDJTI nashriyoti 2005 y.

